

MICROBIAL MEDIATORS OF ECOSYSTEM FUNCTIONS: NITROGEN FIXATION, BIODEGRADATION, AND BIOREMEDIATION

¹Akanksha Bansal, ²Shahla Tanveer

¹Research scholar, Department of Chemistry, St. John's College, Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Agra, India.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Chemistry, Integral University, Lucknow, India.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13842141>

Abstract. *Microorganisms play a pivotal role in ecosystems by driving essential processes such as nitrogen fixation, biodegradation, and bioremediation. Nitrogen-fixing bacteria, such as Azotobacter and Rhizobium, transform atmospheric nitrogen into ammonia, which increases soil fertility and makes nitrogen available to plants. Plant growth and sustainable agriculture depend on this mechanism. Microorganisms like fungi and bacteria break down organic materials during the process of biodegradation, releasing nutrients back into the environment and dissolving contaminants like plastics and hydrocarbons. Furthermore, microbes play a crucial role in bioremediation, which involves cleaning up or detoxifying contaminants from the air, water, and soil to restore ecosystems that have been harmed by heavy metals, oil spills, and industrial waste. These microbial functions support pollution prevention, nutrient cycling, and ecosystem resilience, underscoring the significance of these processes in preserving the sustainability and health of the environment.*

Keywords: *microorganism, Nitrogen-fixing bacteria, Ecosystem, Agriculture.*

INTRODUCTION

Microorganisms may be found anywhere, even in the most unfriendly settings. They are appealing agents for bioremediation because of their capacity to change almost any type of organic material, whether manufactured or natural. However, microbial activity needs certain conditions. Organic pollutants may not break down rapidly in a soil environment for a variety of reasons, including high concentrations of pollutants, a lack of electron acceptors, insufficient nutrient availability, and unfavorable environmental factors like moisture, temperature, pH, ionic strength, or redox status. The majority of organic matter is mineralized aerobically in nature, with oxygen serving as the ultimate electron acceptor. The degradation of organic materials is often the result of a series of steps carried out by several microbes working together or sequentially to bring about the mineralization of the material. The mineralization frequently follows the same pattern as xenobiotics. Slater, J. H. and Lovatt, D. (1984) showed that mixed communities of microorganisms may be more efficient at mineralizing some pollutants, such as chlorinated aromatic hydrocarbons and alkylbenzene sulfonates, than individual species. Sometimes pollutants cannot be directly assimilated by the microbes that oxidize them (co-metabolism) but may instead be further transformed by other populations. These commensal relationships can significantly enhance the mineralization of recalcitrant pollutants and prevent the accumulation of toxic intermediates [1, 2].

NITROGEN FIXATION BY MICROORGANISMS

N₂ is the most abundant gas in Earth's atmosphere, it is extremely unreactive [3]. Biological nitrogen fixation is an important part of the microbial processes [4]. Biological nitrogen fixation

is carried out only by prokaryotes, which may be symbiotic or free living in nature. The process of biological nitrogen fixation, which is facilitated by nitrogenase enzymes, is widely known to be crucial for soil biological activity. The amount of nitrogenase present in the soil is determined by a variety of biological factors, including the ability of particular microbes and plant genotypes to fix nitrogen under different climatic circumstances. On the other hand, nitrogenase activity varies depending on the plant. Free-living, non-photosynthetic aerobic bacteria's ability to fix nitrogen is highly reliant on an abundance of organic C substrates, an oxygen-rich environment, and favorable moisture levels [5].

Nitrogen-fixing organisms are generally active in plant root zone soil. Plants that are capable of releasing exudates exhibit higher nitrogen fixation activity in soil [6]. Before it can be incorporated into biological molecules, N₂ must be chemically reduced to the equivalent of ammonia. The biological reduction of nitrogen is catalyzed by a multimeric enzyme complex, nitrogenase [3]. Nitrogenase consists of two conserved proteins: an iron (Fe) containing dinitrogenase reductase (or Fe protein), encoded by the *nifH* gene and a molybdenum iron (MoFe) dinitrogenase (or MoFe protein) that is encoded by the *nifDK* genes [5]. This enzyme is irreversibly inhibited by molecular oxygen and reactive oxygen species. Oxygen stress on diazotrophic (nitrogen-fixing) organisms triggers a wide range of protective responses aimed at deterring the inhibitory effects of oxygen on nitrogenase. The level of resistance to oxygen stress and the mechanisms involved vary among diazotrophs and influence niche selection. The evolutionary trajectory of adaptive mechanisms that protect nitrogenase from molecular oxygen and reactive oxygen species can be discerned in physiological patterns in microbial morphology, biochemistry, physiology, and community structure along a gradient from anaerobic to fully aerobic environments [3]. Nitrogen-fixing free-living microorganisms have frequently been reported as plant growth promoters [7].

ROLE OF BACTERIA IN MICROORGANISMS

Azotobacter: Even though it may thrive in environments with low O₂ concentrations, *Azotobacter* is an obligate aerobe. This bacterium's ecological spread is a complex topic that depends on several variables that affect whether the organism is present in a particular soil or not [8]. One well-known example of what is known as associative nitrogen fixers is the genus *Azospirillum* of bacteria, which are found in the soils of tropical, subtropical, and temperate climates. These bacteria form intimate connections with the roots of a variety of cultivated and wild plants [9-10].

Rhizobium: *Rhizobium* is known for its ability to establish symbiotic interactions with leguminous plants by the formation and colonization of root nodules, where bacteria fix nitrogen to ammonia and make it available for the plant. The bacteria are mostly rhizospheric microorganisms, despite their ability to live in the soil for a long period [8].

MICROBIAL BIODEGRADATION AND BIOREMEDIATION

The term "microbial biodegradation" describes how microorganisms break down organic materials. By recycling nutrients and lowering pollution, microbes are essential to ecosystems. Enzymes are used by bacteria, fungi, and other microorganisms to convert complex organic materials such as hydrocarbons, polymers, and pesticides into simpler compounds like carbon dioxide and water. The capacity of bacteria, such as *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, and *Mycobacterium*, to break down a wide range of substances via aerobic and anaerobic metabolic pathways makes them particularly important. Fungi are excellent at breaking down lignin and other persistent

organic contaminants. White-rot species such as *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* are one example of this. Applications of biodegradation include sewage treatment, composting, and minimizing landfill trash, where bacteria assist reduce the build-up of hazardous organic compounds [12, 13, 14].

Figure 1. The three groups of nitrogen-fixing organisms include some main genera. In red: genera including symbiotic nitrogen-fixing species; in black: orders or genera (in italics) including free-living nitrogen-fixing species [11].

Microbial Bioremediation is the process of using microorganisms to detoxify and remove pollutants from contaminated environments. This natural and cost-effective method involves microbes metabolizing pollutants into less harmful compounds, making it an essential tool for environmental cleanup. There are two main approaches: in situ bioremediation, where the cleanup occurs at the contamination site, and ex-situ bioremediation, which involves the removal of contaminated material for treatment elsewhere. Specific techniques like bio venting (supplying oxygen to stimulate microbial activity), bioaugmentation (introducing specialized microbes), and phytoremediation (using plants in conjunction with microbes) are commonly applied. Microorganisms like *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* are known for their ability to immobilize or transform toxic heavy metals such as arsenic, lead, and mercury. Meanwhile, bacteria like *Alcanivorax* and fungi such as *Aspergillus* are effective at degrading hydrocarbons in oil spill cleanups. Notable case studies include the use of indigenous bacteria to accelerate oil breakdown after the Exxon Valdez oil spill in 1989 and the bioaugmentation efforts in the Ganges River to mitigate heavy metal contamination [16, 17, 18].

Figure 2. Scheme of Microbial biodegradation of organic pollutants [15]

Figure 3. Microbial Bioremediation has been an efficient process for the removal of heavy metal contaminants. The figure shows various positive aspects and some drawbacks associated with this process over other physicochemical techniques [19].

CONCLUSION

Microorganisms play a crucial role in preserving ecological equilibrium by employing nitrogen fixation and biodegradation. Microbial technological advancements, such as bioremediation, provide long-term solutions for soil enrichment and pollution cleaning.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I express my deep sense of gratitude to my Ph.D. supervisor, Prof. Susan Verghese P., Department of Chemistry, St. John's College, Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Agra for suggesting the problem, valuable guidance, encouragement, and constant help during the study period.

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